

Ecological agro-production grouping of lands spread across the Julfa-Ordubad plain zone

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Abstract: In the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, approximately 70% of the land utilized for cultivated crops is located within the plains and foothill zones. This highlights the necessity of ensuring the efficient and sustainable use of these soils under both cultivated and natural vegetation. The article presents data from various years on soil and agro-ecological research, as well as on the structure and dynamics of the regional land fund. Furthermore, it examines recent land reform initiatives carried out in the area and associated scientific investigations. Based on these studies, the eco-geographical conditions and agro-ecological classification of soils in the Culfa-Ordubad plain region have been established.

Keywords: *soil, agro-production, ecogeography, soil surveys, sloping plain*

Introduction

In recent times, the processes of desertification and land degradation occurring worldwide have had a significant impact on the ecosystems of soils located in the foothill and lowland zones of our country, including the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. As a result of various natural and anthropogenic influences in the region, the degradation of soils has led to a decrease in fertility, a decline in productivity, and the emergence of economic and social difficulties in meeting the food needs of the population.

Therefore, in order to protect the ecological balance of the autonomous republic, it is of great importance to conduct soil-vegetation research in the study area to investigate the ecological condition of the soils located in the foothill and lowland zones of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. (Babayev, 1999: p. 203), (Eyubova, Babayeva, 2005: p. 78)

It is well known that the eco-geographical conditions of an area have a significant impact on the processes of soil formation, its development, and productivity [3, 3-85; 8, 10]. Under the conditions of the autonomous republic, the main eco-geographical factors affecting the soil environment include the geographical location of the area, its relief, geological and geomorphological structure, climate conditions, flora and fauna, anthropogenic influences, and others. The eco-geographical factors mentioned above, both individually and collectively, create spatial variations that lead to the formation of different soil types. From this perspective, in order to ensure the efficient use of soils under cultivated and natural vegetation in the territory of the autonomous republic, it is essential to thoroughly study these factors based on scientific principles. The aforementioned physical-geographical factors have been studied by various researchers in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic from ancient times to the present day for different purposes. However, the study of eco-geographical factors in relation to soil environment protection in Azerbaijan, including the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, was initiated in the mid-20th century by H.A. Aliyev and V.R. Volobuyev.

Since the mid-1980s, under the leadership of Q.Sh. Mammadov in Azerbaijan, research in this field has been expanded by A.H. Valiyev, A.B. Jafarov, and others. Several significant

monographs and methodological manuals of economic importance have been written, utilizing eco-geographical indicators in soil evaluation and the development of soil models. Between 1988 and 1993, S.A. Hajiyevev studied the eco-geographical factors of the gray and chestnut soils spread across the lowland and foothill zones of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, and developed fertility models specifically under forage crops. These findings clearly show that research conducted in this direction within the region is significantly limited compared to the rest of Azerbaijan.

The land fund of the autonomous republic serves as a reflection of the development of the agricultural sector in the region. Therefore, the efficient use of the land fund under cultivated and natural vegetation is considered one of the main priorities in the area. (Jafarov, 2007: p. 57-64).

Materials and Methods

While carrying out the research, the provisions of long-term perspective plans developed in accordance with the new economic reforms and the State Program on land use adopted during the independence period of our country were taken into account. Relevant literature, field data, and map materials related to the distribution of the land fund in the autonomous republic, as well as the causes of desertification and land degradation, were collected.

While working on the topic, the monographs, methodological materials, map resources, and practical experiences that meet modern requirements of scientists who conducted soil and vegetation research in different historical periods in foreign countries, including Azerbaijan and the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, were used.

Analysis and Discussion

The total land fund of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic amounts to 536.300 hectares (as of 01.01.2016). Of this, 479.477 hectares are suitable for agriculture, including 162.391 hectares arable land and 18.409 hectares allocated for household plots, forests, parks, and shrublands. 56.823 hectares consist of bare rocky areas, stony-gravelly lands, and saline soils. These areas are almost not used in agriculture. Out of the arable land, only 60.019.5 hectares are used for crops and perennial plantations, while the remaining 102.371.5 hectares are used as meadows and pastures. As the figures show, due to the mountainous nature of the autonomous republic, arable land constitutes a small portion of the total land area.

In the autonomous republic, approximately 70 percent of the land used for cultivated crops falls within the plains and foothill zones.

For the analysis of the collected literature, maps, and field materials related to the implementation of the topic—particularly in the evaluation of soils and their agro-industrial classification—the tested methodological resources of the following foreign and Azerbaijani scientists have been used. For example, among foreign scholars, the following tested methodological resources have been used: M.F. Fridland (1980), I.M. Godelman (1980, 1981), the work by N.N. Rozova and N.N. Vadkovskaya titled "On the Study of Various Homogeneous Soil Forms" (published in 1984), L.L. Shishov, I.I. Karmanov, and D.N. Durmanov's "Fertility Model and Study of Vineyard Soils" (1986), and the publications by D.S. Bulgakov, N.N. Rozova, and V.I. Remizova on "Modeling of Soil Fertility" (published between 1988–1990), among others.

In the Republic of Azerbaijan, methodological guides published by researchers such as Q.Sh. Mammadov (1990–2005), M.P. Babayev (1990–2000), M.E. Salayev (1980–1990), S.A. Hajiyevev (1998–2000), and others have been used—particularly those focused on the evaluation of soils under cultivated and natural biocenoses, agro-industrial classification, and fertility modeling (Hajiyevev, 2010: p. 296), (İbrahimov, 2005: p. 230)

Soil samples taken from identified areas of the research object were analyzed for the following indicators using the methods of individual soil scientists. Hygroscopic moisture-drying; granulometric composition-pipette after treatment with sodium pyrophosphate; humus-Tyurin; total nitrogen-Kjeldahl; total phosphorus-Gnizburg and Scheglow; absorbed bases-

Schmuck; absorbed calcium and magnesium-Ivanov; absorbed sodium-Hedroits; CO₂-calcimeter; pH (water)-potentiometer, as well as the study of water yield and water-soluble salts in soil and groundwater, methods for calculating dry residue by specific gravity, etc. (Ministry of Ecology and Natural Resources of the Republic of Azerbaijan, 2002, Vol. 1, s. 123)

Chemical analyses of plant samples taken from the area were determined using the methods of the scientists listed below. In feed samples, moisture protein was determined by Kjeldahl, moisture fat by Sokelet apparatus, cell by Genenberg and Steman, hygroscopic moisture and nitrogen-free extractives (NFE) calculation, wet ash burning, etc. methods. In feed samples, moisture protein was determined by Kjeldahl, moisture fat by Sokelet apparatus, cell by Genenberg and Steman, hygroscopic moisture and nitrogen-free extractives (NFE) calculation, wet ash burning, etc. methods. The results of chemical analyses determined in forage plants were used to convert natural forage into feed units.

Medium samples were selected to determine the botanical and chemical composition of the collected herbs. After the plant samples were dried, the dry mass yield was determined by plant species. These indicators were used to determine the productivity of phytocenosis per 1 hectare. We have compared the characteristics and productivity of the cultivated and natural vegetation around the areas where land plots were established with the studies of Prilipko (1970), Iglovikov et al. (1971), Ramenski (1938, 1971), Rabotanov (1960), Sassenkin (1974), Talibov, Ibrahimov (2002, 2009), and others on geobotanical and cultural-technical surveys.

One of the main aspects of carrying out the topic, along with the literature materials, is the collection of field data. Samples were taken from the soil plots established in the research object, analyzed morphologically, and the productivity of cultivated and natural vegetation around these areas was monitored. (Shafibeyov, 1964: p. 204), (Talibov, 2001: p. 192) For this purpose, soil and plant samples were taken, and the productivity of cultivated and natural vegetation around the areas was studied as a result of expeditions organized in May-June 2023 in the Culfa-Ordubad sloping plain. The productivity of ephemerals from the soil areas was determined in mid and late May, while the productivity of wormwood and saline plants was assessed at the end of September and mid-October. In accordance with the research plan, the productivity of cultivated and natural plants was studied at the research site using the methodologies mentioned above for soil evaluation (Table 1).

Table 1: The productivity of cultivated and natural plants (centner per hectare, c/he) in the areas identified in the Culfa-Ordubad inclined plains based on the 2023 data is shown below.

№	The name of the lands	Grain	Clover	Natural herbs
1.	Alluvial-alluvial, meadow-gray	55-60	165-170	7-8
2.	Irrigated sandy loam, weakly saline chestnut	50-55	155-165	6-7
3.	Irrigated light loamy, slightly saline, light brown	45-50	150-155	5-6
4.	Gravelly, sandy brown soils that have been irrigated since ancient times	40-45	140-150	4-5
5.	Gravelly, sandy brown	35-40	130-140	3-4
6.	Gravelly, sandy brown light brown	30-35	125-130	2-3

Based on the soil-plant research conducted in 2023 on the topic "Ecological Conditions of the Culfa-Ordubad Plain Soils," materials collected from various sources (morphological, physical, chemical properties, and ecological conditions) were analyzed, and 36 species varieties were identified in the research object according to specific methodologies. These 36 species varieties were grouped into 14 types and subtypes, with the soils being evaluated and agro-production classification carried out (Table 2).

Table 2. Complete land quality scale of the Julfa-Ordubad sloping plain (on a 100-point scale)

№	The name of the lands	Bonitet score	Score class	Quality team
1.	Light clayey, high, floodplain-alluvial	100	X	I High
2.	Medium loamy, grassy-gray	96	X	
3.	Light loamy, slightly saline chestnut	84	IX	
4.	Gravelly, sandy chestnut	78	VIII	II Good
5.	Light chestnut soils with heavy loam, medium thickness, slightly saline	74	VIII	
6.	Medium loamy, thick, slightly saline light chestnut	66	VII	
7.	Light loamy, thick, slightly non-saline brown	58	VI	III Medium
8.	Sandy, thick, non-saline gravelly brown	56	VI	
9.	Sandy, thick, grayish brown	50	V	
10.	Sandy, thick, gravelly gray-brown	48	V	
11.	Sandy marsh grassland-shrub	44	V	
12.	Sandy marsh-meadow	36	IV	IV Down
13.	Large-volume rocky-gravel river beds	14	II	V Conditionally useless
14.	Salty soils	12	II	

Here, the soils have been evaluated based on the full bonitet scale, with light clayey thin, floodplain-alluvial soils receiving the maximum score of 100, while saline soils received the minimum score of 12.

Conclusion

Summarizing the above, we can obtain the following results.

1. The agro-production classification developed for the research area also allows for the identification of soil groups that require agro-meliorative measures. Overall, this classification encompasses all soil types, subtypes, and species variations found in the Culfa-Ordubad inclined plains.
2. Depending on the complex of environmental conditions of the area, the soils are divided into smaller taxonomic units. As previously mentioned, their final bonitet scores were determined using “correction” coefficients based on factors such as waterlogging, salinization, solonchak formation, erosion, granulometric composition, etc.
3. By knowing the soil type score and agro-production group at the research site, it is possible to determine the implementation of agronomic measures (land reclamation, fertilization, anti-erosion measures, clearing of shrubs and stones, irrigation, etc.) for the improvement of soils used under natural and cultivated vegetation.

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